

Effect of / decisions ...
 Buying / purchases

Daily Carbon Budget is
 function of
 what is
 selected by
 the user

↑ help ppl see that they don't need a new phone to be cool

Flap showing the
provenance of the products

Petra

Meal CO₂
score

Environmental activism

How can we make better ads?

Petra

represent
how long
objects are
expected to
last

Give overview where products come from (or CO₂ emitted, ...)

Arnaud

Lijie Shop → history
 report prix-qualité → line chart
 → time line

Explain where the produce was harvested

how much water/energie is required to grow it

Romane tomatoes
 Transport: 35 km
 Water: 68 liter / kg
 Energie: 4 KWSt / kg

Energy
from lights

projecting at
night, quantity of
electricity wasted.

Streetlights: show how much power the consume

Dieter

Places

Highlight nearby infrastructure which helps to preserve the environment:
- Garbage can
- Next tram stop

Dieter

Garden (park):

history → timeline

surface → ~~scribble~~

no name. dont

plants → ~~scribble~~
tree map.

{ color: types

size: quantity

Lijie

Cars

CO₂ emitted per minute by an Australian
vehicle of this type (or specifically
this vehicle) embedded in the wheels

EVERYTIME A CAR PASSES
THERE: shows the CO₂ released in
the air (proportion)

Morgane

Gas wasted by idling

feedback
readable
or
scam
(phone)

qty of times the taxi drove
without anybody = CO₂

or

CO₂ produced for 1 course divided by nb
of ~~drivers~~
clients

2 hours "à l'arrêt"
but running

4kg CO₂ / individual
+ 1 - average

Data about PLANTS

CO₂ LOSS per each TREE CUTTED
PLACED IN PROXIMITY WITH A CUTTED
TREE

show # animals who benefit
from tree

To
of
pavement
vs
To of
grass
(phone)
with
geo coord.

Garden park:

plants type/year
pruning frequency.
→ bar chart +
timeline.

Lijie

How many trees are there in the city

What is the watering state of the trees and other plants?

Dieter

Arnaud

Tree bubble

positive framing ≠ Co2

HEAT PRODUCED BY CAMP IN TERMS
OF CONTRIBUTION TO GLOBAL WARMING

Federica

Heating
insulation

Overlay thermal imaging on the facade to convey how good the insulation is. Better done in winter.

Dieter

A world in miniature of the neighborhood

Overlay housing-related properties, such as energy consumption, type of heating, facade insulation

Dieter

Data about WATER

Leana

WC restaurant

your use of water

average use of water for flush

ideal amount of water

WATER CLARITY EMBEDDED IN WATER
COLOR (As we NATURAL COLORANT)

Federica

Water quality → composition → bar charts { color = over the limit
(eg. H.O. N.P.)

top
of fountain

shows how
much water
was wasted
since the
beginning
of the year
+ an equivalence
with a lake
or something

Morgane

Transport

Leana

dashboard

kwatt
=
x km

x Co₂
avoided

← riders taken today

To show ppl that the bikes are
in active use & worth checking
out

many of ppl took the bus today and how much carbon emissions it has saved (updates in real time)

Morgane

EACH BIKE IN THE PARKING CONTRIBUTES
TO INCREASE THE LEVEL OF CO₂ SAVED
IF THE BIKE IS NOT THERE IS x% MORE

Federica

show ppl represented in
particle flower by scan-ins

= large panel

→ gamification? each more person taking the tram avoid releasing X CO₂
→ beat this score

ud

Encourage pro-cycling
Behaviour

Dieter

Similar to a step-counter which tracks if the user gets enough exercise, we introduce a personal “resource consumption meter” which tells the user how much environmental resources has been used today.

When considering an action, such as transportation, overlay the resource cost on top of the object under consideration.

For example, the alternatives may be:

- Walking
- Taking the tram
- Taking an e-scooter
- Taking a taxi / own car

The user would also learn the time required to the destination, so a trade-off can be made.

people who drove by
there
here compared to

that walked
properly of ppl

Making an "equivalence" between trains and cars: expressing the numbers of passengers taking the train daily as the numbers of cars it would require

OR
Showing the difference between nb of trains + passengers and nb of cars + passengers that go the same route

trash carbon emission.

in reflection: Shows ~~data~~ data about the average person living here such as average garbage per year (or less if too much)

SCREEN + SENSORS TO DETECT THE
LEVEL OF TRASH ON SITE. VISUALIZING
THE QUANTITY PRODUCE WITH AN "ACCEPTABLE"
WASTE PRODUCTION THRESHOLD

Federica

PREDICTION: 1 VS 10 PEOPLE
LEAVING COKE CANS
ON THE STREET

kg of
waste
collected

kg of
waste collected

• which one
is useless?

+ (with 3D trashbag)

(phone)

Thank of recycle work can paid to non-recycled
♻️ Recycle ♻️
non-recycling ♻️

TRASH QUANTITY PRODUCED BY THE PEOPLE
LIVING IN THE BUILDING, EMBEDDED
IN THE BUILDING HERSELF ITSELF

transparent
trash can

(same as the interactive board:
shows the carbon footprint
of the "waste")

interactive board on which people can draw

EXAMPLE: the image is on empty trash can

fixed

Morgane

and people can draw anything they want in it and it will add the ecological footprint of this "waste"

Lijie wooden boxes → how many trees were consumed → pictograph.

Highlight trash

Encourage observer to dispose of it

Gamification: user gets points for every disposal

Dieter

Petra

Fake data here

Lijie

garbage → carbon emission → bubble chart
Size = quantity
Color = no specific meaning

Pollution

making pollution in the
air visible

Morgane

Morgane

level of pollution when compared to last year's

shows pollution
in the specific
areas

showing impact of dirty
air

"Other"
General
energy / CO2
consumption

How ~~how~~ owns this?
→ Number of previous owners

Lijie La boîte à bon → daily new things → heat map
 → open/close times per day → line chart (at top).
 { color: category.
 { density: stuff items.
 { color: open or close.

proportion of food that was wasted
computed in ~~what~~ what proportion
of the city's population it could
have ~~the~~ fed

Petra

↑
not really footprint

sculpture → city energy consumption → donut charts
{ color: energy category (gas, electric, etc)
| size: proportion of the entire ~~area~~ consumption
compared to

the cycle/cercle is complete when we have consumed all of non-illimited resources of the year

→ today's date

→ last year's date was this happened

Morgane

~~the~~ a more aesthetic version
of a "smiley" face depending
on CO₂ emissions of building

Carbon footprint emitted in this building over time
 (per year) or longer periods
 ENGRAVED

~~Carbon footprint~~ →

Carbon footprint of a building
 = carbon footprint of its inhabitants
 and construction works